

The Franchise Contract And Its Effects In The Light Of The Legislation In Force In The United Arab Emirates: "A Comparative Study"

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 03, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Legislation, United Arab Emirates, The franchise</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6326063</p>	<p><i>The study mainly aimed to identify the legal nature of the franchise contract and its effects in light of the legislation in force in the United Arab Emirates. One of its most important results is as follows:</i></p> <p><i>The franchise contract is distinguished from other similar contracts, especially the licensing contract for the use of the trademark. Some of the UAE laws in force shall be used to solve some of the problems of the franchise contract. However, benefiting from it remains at a minimum until a special law is issued to regulate it. In addition, the UAE legislator is trying to continue to apply the current laws to franchise contracts until it has a clear overview so that he can issue a complete law regulating franchise contracts, free of any obstacles or negatives. Hence, the following most important recommendations are established:</i></p> <p><i>The UAE legislator must take into account the speedy issuance of a special law for the franchise contract. In addition, when enacting such a law, he must take into account that it is characterized by flexibility. This means that it leaves the parties free to set all conditions that do not violate the obligations, rights and duties of the other party. In addition, the governmental or non-governmental bodies interested in the franchise contract must play a tangible role in informing the investors of the importance of the franchise contract and its advantages, whether for themselves, their employees, the consumers or the national economy. In addition, it is required for the UAE to work on a permanent basis to provide national cadres capable of dealing in all fields, whether administrative, legal or commercial. It shall also work continuously to develop these cadres so that they can keep pace with the successive developments in various fields.</i></p>

Introduction

The franchise contract is one of the modern contracts emerged through economic development, the openness of the world to each other, and the removal of borders. Hence, the world became a small village and the era of globalization, technological development and knowledge explosion have arisen. In addition, the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), which paved the way for the gradual emergence of the World Trade Organization (WTO). This led to the reduction and decline of small-sized projects. Hence, the global trade has penetrated global markets by relying on large-sized and transcontinental institutions to reach the required expansion in light of the fierce competition between those institutions.^(*)

Franchise contracts are concluded in order to achieve expansion and spread for owners of large, successful, reputable and commercial projects without additional financial or administrative burdens. Hence, it enables the other party who obtains the commercial concession to own and operate a commercial activity in which it enjoys complete independence. It shall also pick up where others have finished or achieved successes, business reputation. It is also supported by technical and administrative assistance in addition to the experience of the franchisors. Thus, the franchise system achieves the interests of the franchisor and the franchisee. It is also characterized by the development and improvement of investment mechanisms. In order to achieve the interest of the parties or the two parties to the franchise contract, the franchisor is benefited from spreading in different and diverse markets to reach without investing large sums of money. Also, on the other hand, the franchisee is benefited from the reputation and fame of the franchisors and the services and products achieving profits that it would not have achieved alone in a short time. Therefore, it is not surprising that the areas of franchise cover wide sectors of different activities: health, education, cleaning and maintenance services, and other various sectors. Accordingly, and pursuant to the International Franchise Organization, the franchise has contributed to

* Al-Bishtawi, Doaa Tariq Bakr, (2008), **Franchise Contract** and Its Effects, Master's Thesis, College of Graduate Studies, An-Najah National University, Palestine.

fundamental changes in more than (85) aspects of business, including products and services applied in more than (100) countries around the world. It is estimated that franchise projects represent more than (50%) of the world's retail business models[†]

The traditional ideas linked the lack of development and the scarcity of capitals collapsed, as successive developments proved that growth and economic development are not primarily based on capital. Rather, they are based on the field of technology and information in addition to capital, where technology is the trump card for its success, development and improvement.[‡] Accordingly, the advanced countries in the field of industry realized the importance of technology and knowledge as a main strategic resource in all fields. It became a major source of income for the advanced countries. This led them to invest huge sums in the field of technology and knowledge through their scientific research centers, until they had a huge stock of technology and knowledge in various fields in such a short time, which made them a global leader. Hence, they were able to impose its control over the majority of developing countries[§].

Study Problem:

Study Problem deals with the identification of the legal nature of the franchise contract and its effects in light of the legislation of the United Arab Emirates, for the problems raised by the franchise contract, represented in the absence of legal regulation. This is in addition to the difficulty of determining the legal nature of this contract, and addressing the dispersion of the legal aspects that determine the nature of the contract and its effects on the contractors in the legislation of the United Arab Emirates. In addition, the problem lies in the basic difficulty about clarifying the rights and obligations arising from this contract, and the waste of the rights of the parties represented by it. Hence, the Arab legal systems, including the United Arab Emirates, did not include a legal system specific to this contract, which requires research into the extent to which the general provisions in these legal systems are absorbed in their existing status of the franchise contract and its effects. Hence, the judicial rulings issued in disputes related to the franchise contract are very few. Based on the foregoing, the study problem was able to answer the following main question:

What is the legal nature of the franchise contract and its effects in light of the legislation in force in the United Arab Emirates?

Several sub-questions are derived from the main question, as follows:

1. What is the importance of the legal concept of the franchise contract, and determining its effects in light of the legislation in force in the United Arab Emirates?
2. What are the different types of franchise contract?
3. What are the most important problems facing the franchise contract, and the most important basic principles to be taken into account when drafting the contract?

Objectives of the study:

The study mainly aims to identify the legal nature of the franchise contract and its effects in light of the legislation in force in the United Arab Emirates. The following sub-objectives emerge from the main objectives of the study:

- 1- Identifying the importance of the legal concept of the franchise contract, and determining its effects in light of the legislation in force in the United Arab Emirates.
- 2- Indicating the different types of franchise contract.
- 3- Disclosing the problems facing the franchise contract, and the basic principles to be taken into account when drafting the contract.

Importance of the Study:

The importance of the study is characterized in the study of the franchise contract. It is considered one of the most important contracts through which the economy of many countries, especially developing countries, is moved, and promoted to reach the ranks of producing countries. It also introduces the role established under this contract to the concerned parties and officials, through which the economic growth is accelerated. This is in addition to its connection to a new type of trade, which is the transfer of knowledge and technology, which has become imposing itself strongly on our contemporary society. It is based on that the number of dealers is increasing day by day and at a great speed. Moreover, the volume of financial transactions, conducted through it exceeds billions by far. This contract also contributes significantly to providing many job opportunities to confront the problem of unemployment, and to raise the efficiency of the workforce through the trainings it receives from the franchisor. This leads to the preservation of the national capital and not to emigrate abroad. It

[†] Al-Ghamdi, Abdul Hadi Muhammad, (2010), Legal Aspects of the Franchise Contract, Journal of the Faculty of Law for Legal and Economic Research, No. (2), p. 909-948.

[‡] .Abdu, Elsayed Ibrahim Ahmed, (2017), The Franchise Contract in the Light of the Provisions of Private International Law, Ph.D. thesis, Mansoura University - Cairo, p. 7.

[§] .Abdu, Elsayed Ibrahim Ahmed, (2017), Ibid., p. 7.

enables researchers and specialists to benefit from the information contained in the franchise contract, as well as to benefit from many colleges such as law, business administration and Economics colleges.

Study Methodology:

This study is based on the use of the descriptive, analytical and comparative approach, where the franchise contract and then the legal nature of the franchise contract are described, in addition to distinguishing between the franchise contract and other similar contracts. Then, the obligations of the parties covered by the franchise contract and the effects of the expiry of this contract term are analyzed, in order to indicate the opinions of jurists on the franchise concept. This aims at reaching results that are based on a scientific aspect that includes accuracy and clarity in providing appropriate recommendations. It also aims at using the comparative approach to compare the legal systems in which such contracts are concluded to reach the most important aspects of the difference among legal systems, such as the United Arab Emirates, Egypt, Jordan, France and the United States of America.

Study plan:

The first topic: the concept and importance of the franchise contract

The first requirement: the concept of the franchise contract.

The second requirement: the importance of the franchise contract.

The second topic: the legal nature and the challenges facing the franchise contract.

The first requirement: the legal nature of the franchise

The second requirement: the challenges facing franchise contracts.

Conclusion

Findings and recommendations

The first topic: the concept and importance of the franchise contract

Introduction and Division:

The franchise contract is one of the new technologies that replaced some commercial activities in their traditional forms, as the Americans re-used the French term "franchise", which was widely used in the Middle Ages and then became forgotten in the 20th century. This term was materialized on the legal and economic levels, especially in the period following the Second World War^(*). The franchise contract has attracted the attention of many researchers and specialists in the modern era. As for this topic, more details on this topic shall be highlighted through the following claims:

The first requirement: the concept of the franchise contract.

The second requirement: the importance of the franchise contract.

The first requirement: the concept of the franchise contract.

The word "Franchise" is a French word derived from the verb "Affranchir, meaning "free of servitude". It was used for the first time in the Middle Ages, as previously explained, to describe the rights and privileges granted to the ruler of the region in exchange for allowing the establishment of markets, fairs, and the transfer of rights through other regions. The French Franchise Federation, issued in 1972 has been considered as it included the obligation that must be considered by the franchisors. In addition, the franchise is a method of cooperation between two projects, namely: the franchisor, which is the "party that grants its trade name, trademark and work system" to the franchisee which is the "beneficiary party that pays the franchise fee". This is in addition to a percentage of its total sales in return for obtaining the right to use the name, the logo, and the work system of the franchisor in a specific region and for a specific period, which is the contract term concluded between the two parties, which includes the following for the first party^(††).

1. Ownership or right to use marks to attract clients, whether they are trademarks, industrial brands, logos, company name, trade name or symbols.
2. Using technical, and acquired knowledge and experience.
3. A group of products/services or technology.

The International Franchise Federation defined it as: "A contractual relationship concluded between the two parties whereby the first party (the franchisor) is obliged to maintain a continuous interest in the business of the second party (franchisee) in many areas, such as technical knowledge and training. The franchisee works under a well-known trade name, and through a form or control procedures with the knowledge of the first party, provided that the franchisee finances its activity from its sources. The European Franchise Federation defines it as "a system for marketing goods, services or technology based on permanent and close cooperation between two financially and legally independent parties, the franchisor and the franchisee, according to which the first party grants - in return for direct or indirect performance - the right to the second party. This is in order to carry out the work in accordance with a special way using the name, trademark or brand, as well as technical knowledge,

^{**} Al-Najjar, Muhammad Mohsen Ibrahim, (2007), Commercial Franchise Contract, New University House, Egypt, p. 7-8.

^{††} Al-Hadidi, Yasser Sayed, (2014), The Legal System of the Franchise, Dar Al-Fikr Al-Arabi, Amman, Jordan, p. 19.

commercial methods, technical and procedural systems, and other intellectual property and industrial rights, supported by commercial and technical assistance for the term of the franchise agreement concluded for this purpose^(††).

The International Federation defines the franchise process as: “a contractual relationship between two parties, the franchisor and the franchisee, whereby the franchisor is obligated to transfer knowledge and training to the franchisee, performed under a known name, or form of procedures owned or controlled by the franchisor. In this contract, the franchisee invests its money in the work, subject matter of the franchise, so that the risks of the success of this operation are solely borne by it^(§§).”

Thus, it is “a contract under which a person, the franchisor, is entrusted with teaching another person, called the franchisee, the practical knowledge, which includes the transfer of technical knowledge, providing technical assistance, and authorizing it to use its trademark and supply it with goods from the supplier. This is in addition to the franchisee’s obligation to pay the price, non-competition and confidentiality.”^(***)

In the judiciary, it is defined as “a method of dealing between two or more commercial institutions, one of which is a franchisor and the other is a franchisee, according to which the first party, the owner places a known name or trademark or initials, or industrial, commercial or service symbols or marks, as well as special technical knowledge - at the disposal of the other party. In addition, it shall have the right to use a group of products or services, original or special, in return for a fee or an advantage gained compulsorily and completely exploiting them according to exclusively selected and controlled commercial techniques, achieving the best effect in the classified market and obtaining rapid growth of the commercial activity of the concerned institutions^(†††).” In jurisprudence, it is defined as “a contract under which the assignor grants the right of spatial exclusivity to sell its products by the assignee, with the latter’s commitment to the exclusive supply by the assignor.”^(†††)

Bearing the foregoing in mind, the researcher considers, under the definition of franchise, that it is a contract concluded between two parties called the licensor, and another party called the licensee. Hence, it allows or requires the licensee to practice a certain business during a specific period under a specific name belonging to the licensee, owned by it or associated to it.

The second requirement: the importance of the franchise contract

Its importance is due to the spread on a scale by which the contract is characterized, through the following:

The importance of the franchise contract:

1. Increasing the activity and development of the commercial field within the state, and then increasing the investments, which in turn play a very important role in the advancement of the countries’ economy^(§§§). In return, it works to enrich the other party. Therefore, many companies and individuals resort to it, as well as the state, to develop its economic field within the framework of this new system^(****).
2. It works to transfer knowledge and technical expertise to the licensee, which it uses in turn to create and develop products and services. Therefore, allowing the owner of technical expertise or the trademark to transfer this knowledge and the licensee benefiting from the commercial reputation of this trademark itself is the main element in the spread of this contract. It also resulted in having many institutions resort to using it to develop their companies, given that this feature is not available in other contracts.^(††††)

^{††} Al-Hadidi, Yasser Sayed, (2014) p.21

^{§§} Al-Kandari Mahmoud Ahmed, The Most Important Practical Problems Facing Franchising Contract, p.5

^{***} Tawfiq Khalfaoui, (2015), Franchise Contract, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Larbi Ben M'hidi University, Oum El Bouaghi, p. 17

^{†††} Al-Hadidi, Yasser Sayed (2014) p.26

^{††††} Al-Ukaili, (2015), Explanation of Commercial Law, House of Culture for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan, p. 237.

^{§§§§} Sof, Mohamed Mouloud, (2015), The Franchise Contract and Its Effects, Master Thesis, Faculty of Law, Zagazig University, Cairo, Egypt, p. 5 .

^{****} Mokhtaria, Hajji, (2018), Excellence Contract in Algerian Administrative Law, Master's Thesis, Faculty of Law and Political Science, Saida University, Algeria, p. 6 .

^{†††††} Hillel, Munir Ali, (2020), Legal Aspects of the Franchise Contract, Journal of Economic, Administrative and Legal Sciences, Volume (3), Issue (5), p. 112-113. Quoted from Al-Sabri, Faisal Ahmed Abdullah, (2020), The Role of the Franchise Contract in Technology Transfer, The National Center for Legal Publications, Cairo, p. 8-9.

3. It is one of the mechanisms through which the integration of projects of all kinds is achieved, as through this integration, countries and companies can conquer new markets, whether simple or strong markets without fear of lack of competition^(††††).

Al-Amiri (2017) points out that the importance of the franchise contract lies in the light of the concept of contemporary trade in various fields, which can be addressed as follows:^(§§§§)

- ✓ The franchise system provides multiple job opportunities for many workers, thus reducing unemployment.
- ✓ Providing a wide variety of goods and services at prices suitable for everyone, through commercial centers and factories, established according to the franchise system.
- ✓ Expanding the scope of trade exchanges between countries, reviving the economy, and encouraging investment.
- ✓ The transfer of technical knowledge, the exchange of competencies and experiences, and strengthening the principle of commercial competition and hence achieving tangible economic prosperity for peoples.

The second topic: the legal nature and challenges of the franchise contract

Introduction and Division:

To commence and achieving the commercial activity, the merchant uses a number of persons, including those who are related to them under employment contracts that put them in the position of an affiliate, such as employees or users. Those persons carry out commercial work in the name and account of the merchant. Some of them are those whom the merchant uses to dispose of its products or send the goods and services it needs or mediate between it and other customers. Those persons are linked to the merchant by work contracts. They are often professional in performing these works for others. They then work independently, such as agents by commission and brokers, and there are those who represent merchants^(*****).

The first requirement: the legal nature of the franchise contract

The franchise contract is subject to more than one law or legal regulation, depending on its subject. It is primarily subject to contract law, as it requires the consent of both parties, their approval and acceptance. It is subject to the laws of distribution contracts in terms of being a distribution contract, especially if it includes conditions of exclusivity, and licenses of the trademark and other elements of intellectual property such as the patent or the right of invention. Hence, they are subject to the corresponding laws. The licensing of the trademark is subject to the duty of registration in order for it to be entered into effect towards persons. This applies to the aspect of the franchise contract. In addition, the contract that proves the agreement between the two parties in relation to the franchise contract reflects all aspects of the franchise contract and contains the terms of its organization. There are often a number of appendices to the franchise agreement detailing distribution and marketing plans, and all the elements that need detailed evidence that the franchisor must adhere to.^(†††††)

As a result of the absence of legislative texts regulating the franchise contract, there is no single law that applies to all its aspects. Rather, there were some laws and regulations that deal with some of its aspects, such as competition and anti-trust laws. The burden of finding legal solutions to the problems due to its implementation fell on the judiciary and jurisprudence, similar to other contracts whose provisions were not issued by the legislator. Initially, the French judiciary referred to subjecting the franchise contract to the provisions of the sales contract.^(†††††) Another opinion from the jurisprudence was established that the franchise contract is one of the supply contracts. Rather, we find many differences between them and conclude that it is not possible in any way to apply the provisions of the supply contract to the franchise contract or any other contracts thought to be similar to it.

In the absence of defining the legal nature of the franchise contract, given that it is a novel contract created by modern technology and scientific progress in this field, and the people's need for this type of contract,

††††† Al-Hadidi, Yasser Sayed, (2010), *The Franchise Contract in the Light of Competition Legislation and Prevention of Monopolistic Practices: A Comparative Study*, Police Academy, Police Press, Cairo, p. 5.

§§§§ Al-Amiri, Rashad Noaman Shaye, (2017), *The Legal Framework for the Franchise Commercial License Contract, The Position of the Yemeni Project*, Journal of Social Studies, Volume (23), Issue (3), pp. 101-120.

***** Al-Ghamdi, Abdul Hadi Muhammad, (2010), *Legal Aspects of the Franchise Contract*, Journal of the Faculty of Law for Legal and Economic Research, No. (2), p. 909-948.

††††† Al-Ahmar, Kanaan, (2003), *Trademark Licensing and Franchise Contracts*, WIPO National Symposium, Trademarks, World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), Damascus, December 22 and 23, p. 8.

††††† Khaled Dhaif Allah Al-Otaibi, (2008), *Legal Relationships Arising from the Franchise Contract*, Ph.D. thesis, Amman Arab University, Amman, p. 38.

this contract is not similar to other commercial contracts. And if we find that the laws in Arab countries apply the provisions of contracts that we think are similar to franchise contracts, we however see otherwise. The contract is governed by the terms and conditions of the agreement concluded between the two parties to the contract, as this concluded agreement is the main reference for the two parties to the contract in terms of the rights and obligations of both parties as long as it does not contain any violations of the legislation. In the end, it is an application of the principle of freedom in contracting. In addition, the Arab countries must establish a special law for franchising. Attempting to apply the provisions of other contracts because of what is thought to be a similarity between the franchise contract and other contracts are futile attempts due to the distinction of this contract from other contract^(§§§§§).

Franchise has been concluded in the Arab countries with the Kentucky Fried Chicken Company (KFC), then Pepsi-Cola, Hard Rock, Pizza Hut, McDonald's, and oil companies with gas stations, and more.

Many studies have shown that there are dozens of Saudi and UAE companies working in all fields, and they have proven their success and qualifications to work with this system, and then the possibility of their spread within the Arab countries. Their trading volume is in billions of dollars. In general, it can be said that the number of the franchisor companies in the Arab region does not exceed five companies, while all the elements of successful franchising are available in many companies in the Arab region, including the continuous increase in sales, high profitability and credibility, practical experiences, in addition to the global acceptance of commodities traded in the Arab markets^(*****).

The first requirement: the challenges facing franchise contracts

One of the general negative effects of the franchise system is unfair competition between new activities established in the franchise system, and the expected damage to similar local commercial and service activities, currently established, which may negatively affect their growth due to the imbalance in the capabilities available to each of them. Among the challenges that can be mentioned, but not limited to, are the following:

- ✓ The existence of interests conflict between the two parties to this contract, as each of the parties seeks to include the terms that guarantee its interests in the contract, as the franchisor seeks to set conditions that protect it and its technical expertise, knowledge and secrets, and prevent its transfer to its competitors. The franchisor also sometimes establishes some conditions that maintain its economic superiority by setting conditions that limit and reduce its competitiveness and not expand its commercial activity to an extent more than necessary^(†††††).
- ✓ As for the franchisee, the situation is different, as it seeks to obtain the technical expertise, knowledge and training necessary exclusively for it and not others in order to take full advantage of the franchise contract^(†††††).
- ✓ The franchise contract may lead to the exploitation of the weak party, which is the franchisee and the limitation of access to technology or the right to introduce improvements to it. This which negatively affects all competitors, especially the conditions that limit freedom of competition and market sharing, limit entry to these markets and control market prices and prevent them from being determined. This eventually materializes into economic domination, which harms the national economy of the weak party^(§§§§§).

Conclusion

In conclusion of this study, we have explained the concept of the franchise contract, its importance, and its legal basis, as it is an innovative and modern method on the one hand, and a new contract for the need and the variable and developing commercial activity on the other hand. From this point of view, the study gave a clear idea of the franchise contract, and its legal impacts with a descriptive analytical approach, as well as a work method for which this contract dates back to the Middle Ages. However, it has become a recent development to become a self-established system, with ethics and behaviors in addition to some laws and regulations that organized its aspects. The specialists did not establish a unified and comprehensive concept of this contract.

Study Results:

§§§§§ Aisha Al Haidos, (2020), The Legal Nature of the Franchise Contract: A Comparative Study, Master Thesis, Qatar University .

***** Al-Bishtawi, Doaa Tariq Bakr, (2008), Ibid., p. 13.

††††† Jilali, Youssef, The Legal System of the Franchise Contract: A Comparative Study, Ibid., p. 16.

††††† Shobaki, Muhammad Jamal Muhammad, (2015) The tax dealing with franchise contracts with both parts (administrative franchise "B.O.T" and franchise, Master's thesis, An-Najah National University, College of Graduate Studies, Palestine, p. 43.

§§§§§ Jilali, Youssef, The Legal System of the Franchise Contract: A Comparative Study, Ibid., p. 17.

1. The franchise contract is distinguished from other similar contracts, especially the licensing contract to use the trademark.
2. The franchise contract has not received special legal legislation in force in the United Arab Emirates until now.
3. Some of the UAE laws in force shall be used to solve some of the problems of the franchise contract. However, benefiting from it remains at a minimum until a special law is issued to regulate it.
4. The franchise contract is a complex commercial contract that has its own nature, and it cannot be reduced to a single legal template or given a specific legal character to it, as it is characterized by development and renewal.
5. There is no doubt that the franchise entails the transfer of knowledge and modern technology to the Emirati society. This increases the level of progress of the state and raises the standard of living and services. It also opens many fields of work that accommodate the workforce in the state at all its technical and administrative levels.
6. The UAE legislator is trying to continue applying the current laws to franchise contracts until it has a clear overview so that he can issue a complete law regulating franchise contracts, free of any obstacles or negatives.

Study recommendations:

- 1- Encouraging more investors to engage in all commercial fields according to the franchise system without fearing that their projects will be exposed to obstacles and then lose their rights due to the existence of a clear law from the beginning that clearly defines the rights and obligations of each party.
- 2- The UAE legislator must take into account the speedy issuance of a special law for the franchise contract. In addition, when enacting such a law, he must take into account that it is characterized by flexibility. This means that it leaves the parties free to set all conditions that do not violate the obligations, rights and duties of the other party. In addition, the governmental or non-governmental bodies interested in the franchise contract must play a tangible role in informing the investors of the importance of the franchise contract and its advantages, whether for themselves, their employees, the consumers or the national economy.
- 3- The need for the UAE to work on a permanent basis to provide national cadres capable of dealing in all fields, whether administrative, legal or commercial. It also works continuously to develop these cadres so that they can keep pace with the successive developments in various fields.

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